

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION IN LANGUAGE LEARNING: TIPS FOR SPEAKING FLUENCY

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ABSTRACT

This article gives overview of development of communicative skills of professional English, personal motivations of the student, how to create conditions for more effective language acquisition and development of communication skills.

Introduction

Today, a foreign language is a bridge that unites different groups of people with different interests. In addition, a foreign language has become an integral part of many professions and as a discipline is included in the mandatory program in any higher educational institution. People began to understand that for personal development, you also need to learn one of the foreign languages.

One of the main goals of teaching a foreign language is to develop students' communicative skills. Communicative teaching of foreign languages involves teaching based on tasks aimed at developing communicative skills. This means that the learning process should be structured in such a way as to imitate the communication process as much as possible. Participation in such interaction requires mastering oral speech in a foreign language, which includes developing speaking skills.

Tips for speaking fluency. There are different ideas of how to improve communicative skills of students studying technical sciences. One of them is CLIL (content language integrated learning). "The advantage of using CLIL approach gives opportunity to the learners to increase knowledge and practice the language skills by using language in different contexts of their specialty"¹. But it has its own disadvantages as "insufficient number of class hours, difficulties

¹ Kuvandikova Kh . Implementation of CLIL in language learning and teaching process
<http://grnjournals.us/index.php/AJSHR pp.167-168>.

in forming groups with English as the language of instruction, high requirements for knowledge of the language and the lack of continuity in the application of this approach²”.

Students studying in technical universities often face difficulties in expressing their thoughts. Especially if it is professionally oriented speaking, where the student uses terminology. Therefore, it is important, within the framework of foreign language classes, to use methodological techniques that promote communication training, which have a pedagogical effect only if the teacher can clearly formulate tasks, effectively use teaching tools and create comfortable conditions for speech activity. This includes creating an atmosphere in which students strive to listen to foreign speech and speak in a foreign language, and also have the opportunity to freely express their thoughts without creating a language barrier.

One of such techniques can be the creation of speech situations that will definitely arouse interest in the task. For this, you can use short videos, podcasts where students themselves voice the process, i.e., perform dubbing. After dubbing, you can ask the group control questions.

1. In the tool shop: <https://youtu.be/mVTjygCLyYg> Parts of a Lathe Machine

1. What is head stock?
2. What is chuck(jaw)?
3. What is cross slide?
4. What is carriage?
5. What is the function of a compound rest?
6. What part is Bed?
7. Where is Tail stock?
8. When is feed rod used?

2. <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/xSl2mpbWbc0?feature=share>

After watching this video the teacher asks the group the question “What is CNC Machining?”. The students take turns describing this type of machine, complementing each other. (Possible description of the CNC)

“CNC stands for computer numerical control. So, CNC machining is any kind of machining process controlled by a computer. Computerized automation allows parts to be made more quickly, accurately, precisely, and with more complex geometries than those produced via manual machining. CNC also reduces manual machining labor that would otherwise be done by humans. While they aren’t machining each part themselves, people are essential for programming and operating the machines, ensuring that every operation goes smoothly”.

3. <https://www.youtube.com/shorts/JY7UIQBSNik?feature=share>

The teacher can also suggest watching a video fragment of the work of the Derrickman, after which the students conduct a discussion among themselves, or a discussion in small groups. Based on the video fragment, the student can create a monologue on a given professional topic.

The teacher also asks questions that touch on the information mentioned in the video: Derrickman job. Describe what kind of work does he do? Where does he sit?

² Kuvandikova Kh . Implementation of CLIL in language learning and teaching process
<http://grnjournals.us/index.php/AJSHR> pp.167-168.

4.Round table discussions. Students and a teacher can arrange a round table discussion of the topic "Artificial intelligence and its impact on society". This learning situation can be considered professionally oriented, since engineers often participate in project discussions in a round table format, including with foreign colleagues. This exercise will help students develop argumentation and critical thinking skills, as well as improve their command of professionally oriented vocabulary. The teacher manages the meeting, by a pre-prepared scenario and at the same time reveals the potential communicative capabilities of each participant. Examples of topics may also include general engineering topics like :

1.What are the potential impacts of renewable energy on the oil and gas industry in the next decade?

2.How is technology expected to change the exploration and extraction processes in the oil and gas sector?

3.What role do you think geopolitical factors will play in the future of oil and gas markets?

4.How will the demand for oil and gas evolve with the rise of electric vehicles and alternative fuels?

5.How do you expect the workforce in the oil and gas industry to change in response to new technologies and market demands?

There are always students with a lower level of English in the groups. Naturally, this requires a differentiated approach. Multi-level tasks, taking into account the individual capabilities of each student, also affect the development of students' individual creative abilities. I use the following personality-oriented questions that encourage students to express their opinions based on their own experience:

1.What do you think successful learning means to you?

2. What qualities do you think are important for achieving your academic goals?

3. What is your most vivid experience in your academic life, and what did you learn from it?

4. How do you cope with difficulties in your studies, and what helps you with this?

5. What subject do you like the most, and what exactly attracts you to it?

6. How do you see your future after graduating from University?

7. What does it mean to you to be part of society?

Usage of **provocative statements** that ensure the full involvement of students in the discussion of the topic are also effective.. They encourage them to express their point of view on a particular issue, to argue it, to disagree with the "provocation" and are of great importance for the development of students' speech in foreign language classes.

1.Is it possible to make people work better?

2.What challenges do you expect at work?

3.What new things are you going to bring to the job?

4.What is the first goal you will set when you come to work? What will you do if you have to reduce your salary by 10%?

5.How do you hope to advance at work?

6.Do you like to work in a team?

Conclusion

The process of teaching English in technical universities always faces problems of different levels, which affect the level of professional competence of students. The personal

motivations of the student, the general level of language training, educational resources, and of course the experience of the teacher play a huge role. “We should underline that motivation of learners increased to the extent that they learn special content, they became interested in the meaning of words while translating specific texts. It became easier for them to make dialogues or conversations on topics covering their major, using specific terms and structures”³.

For students, the main difficulty in mastering the language is the abundance of technical terminology. It is the professionally-oriented approach to teaching English that will minimize difficulties and place a greater emphasis on the professional skills and competence needed for the future profession.

Thus, an individual attitude towards each student, the use of various methods, technologies and materials will create conditions for more effective language acquisition and development of communication skills. Adaptation of materials and tasks for students of different levels will allow to take into account the individual needs and abilities of students. The teacher must create comfortable conditions for identifying the abilities and development of each student in a group and ensure the achievement of the desired results.

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³ Kuvandikova Kh.B. Problems,Solution and Development of ESP in Uzbekistan, International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, p.211